

THE THEORETICAL BASIS OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES IN TEACHING CHEMISTRY

Tojiboyeva Munisa Akmal qizi

Chirchik State Pedagogical University

Faculty of Natural Sciences

3rd year student of Chemistry Education

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-9154-696X>

E-mail: tojiboyeva.m1661@gmail.com

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Abstract: This article analyzes the role and importance of modern pedagogical approaches in teaching chemistry. Based on a comparative analysis of traditional teaching methods and modern methods, the effectiveness of new pedagogical technologies in increasing students' interest in science, developing independent thinking and practical skills is highlighted. The advantages of innovative organization of chemistry lessons through interactive methods, STEAM approach, digital platforms, problem-based learning and project work are shown. The article also provides recommendations for improving chemistry lessons in secondary school settings. The results of the study justify the possibility of increasing the effectiveness of teaching chemistry based on new approaches.

Keywords: Chemistry education, modern pedagogical approaches, STEAM, problem-based learning, gamification, digital technologies, virtual laboratory, differentiated learning, project-based learning, interdisciplinary integration.

ENTRANCE

Chemistry, with its fundamental importance and practical aspects, occupies a significant place in various spheres of human life. Chemistry allows students to study chemical processes and their laws, understand changes in the environment, and contribute to the modern development of science and technology. Chemistry education not only provides scientific knowledge, but also develops students' logical thinking and creative approaches, and they also learn to connect various natural sciences and technologies. The modern education system is striving to implement new pedagogical technologies on a global scale. Abandoning traditional approaches to teaching chemistry and using new pedagogical methods and innovative technologies increases the effectiveness of the educational process. This, in turn, allows students to effectively organize chemistry education using methods such as interdisciplinary integration, problem-based learning, the STEAM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Art, Mathematics) approach, gamification, digital technologies, and virtual laboratories.

In order to develop students' scientific abilities and prepare them to solve various problems that they face today, modern pedagogical approaches are important in chemistry education. This in itself creates the opportunity to effectively organize students' educational activities, as well as increase their interest and motivation in science. Teaching chemistry using modern approaches develops not only students' scientific knowledge, but also their practical skills and creative abilities. In this process, the use of new pedagogical technologies, innovative methods and advanced techniques allows students to freely express their thoughts, improve their creative and analytical thinking skills. The main goal of modern chemistry education, in addition to providing students with scientific knowledge, is to prepare them to work independently, solve problems on a scientific basis, generate new ideas and conduct scientific research. Therefore, this study analyzes the issue of new pedagogical approaches used in teaching chemistry and how they affect educational effectiveness.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

To improve the effectiveness of chemistry education, it is necessary to introduce modern pedagogical technologies and conduct a thorough analysis of scientific research. Various pedagogical methods and approaches play an important role in improving the quality of chemistry education and developing students' thinking processes. This section analyzes the scientific foundations and practical application of modern pedagogical approaches in chemistry education. STEAM education. STEAM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Art, Mathematics) education involves the integration of science and technology with art and mathematics. This approach helps to develop innovative thinking, logical analysis and creative thinking in students. STEAM methodology provides interdisciplinary integration in chemistry education and gives students the opportunity to simultaneously consolidate scientific and practical knowledge. In this approach, chemistry is connected with other disciplines, such as physics, biology, ecology and engineering. Theoretically, STEAM education develops students' social, technical, and scientific skills, as well as helps them solve problems based on scientific approaches. The importance of integrating STEAM education into chemistry education in developing students' creative thinking has been analytically highlighted[1].

Problem-Based Learning (PBL). The problem-based learning methodology provides students with the opportunity to solve real-life problems and develops their independent thinking, analysis, and problem-solving skills. The main goal of the PBL method is to provide students with the opportunity to actively participate

in solving scientific and practical problems. In chemistry, this method is aimed at students performing practical tasks such as analyzing chemical processes encountered in everyday life, solving environmental problems based on chemical solutions, and studying the composition of food products. By implementing the PBL method, students' practical skills and scientific analysis skills increase, which increases the effectiveness of education[2].

Digital technologies and virtual laboratories. The development of information and communication technologies has opened up new opportunities in the educational process. The use of digital technologies in chemistry education allows students to learn chemistry experiments safely and effectively. With the help of virtual laboratories, students have the opportunity to simulate and analyze chemical reactions without having to work with expensive reagents or dangerous chemicals . This method helps students learn chemistry in a practical way, while also allowing them to safely perform laboratory work at home or in the classroom[3].

Gamification and game-based learning. Gamification methods are designed to make the learning process interesting and interactive. Introducing game elements to students increases their motivation and makes the learning process more effective. In chemistry, gamification can be used to develop students' abilities to remember chemical elements, study chemical reactions, or perform laboratory work. Learning about chemicals through an educational game or quiz allows students to assess their knowledge [4].

Project-based learning. Project-based learning is an approach that helps students solve real-life problems. In chemistry education, project-based learning teaches students how to chemically produce natural dyes, conduct research on renewable energy sources, and find scientific solutions to other global problems. The study of project-based learning has shown how it is useful in developing students' independent research and creative thinking skills [5].

DISCUSSION

Modern pedagogical approaches create new opportunities in teaching chemistry and make the process of acquiring knowledge more effective for students. Each of them has its own advantages and methods of application , which help to develop students' thinking skills, conduct independent scientific research, and form problem-solving skills during the educational process . The main goal of each approach is the student's personal development, deepening their knowledge, and forming abilities based on scientific thinking.

The STEAM approach creates opportunities for interdisciplinary integration in chemistry education. The main advantage of the STEAM model is that students not only learn chemistry theoretically, but also learn to apply it in practice. For example, solving environmental problems based on chemical research provides students with important knowledge and develops practical skills. In this approach, students are taught to use a creative approach to solving problems. The application of the STEAM approach to chemistry education allows students to understand technology and science together, which leads to a completely new formation of knowledge [1].

Problem-based learning (PBL) helps students develop skills in solving real-life problems. In this approach, students use scientific methods to analyze various problems on a scientific basis and solve them. Problem-based learning methodology allows students to develop independent thinking, analyze and develop scientific solutions. One of the advantages of using the PBL method in chemistry is that students can fully consolidate their knowledge. Students actively participate in analyzing chemical processes encountered in life and developing new knowledge, which makes the learning process more effective [2].

Digital technologies and virtual laboratories create the opportunity to make the educational process interactive and interesting. Today, the study of chemistry with the help of technology has become more effective in many ways . Virtual laboratories allow students to safely simulate chemical reactions. Also, with the help of Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR) technologies, students have the opportunity to see chemicals and reactions in three-dimensional format. These technologies help students visualize the learning process and contribute to a deeper understanding of knowledge [3].

Gamification is an effective tool for increasing student motivation. Students learn chemistry through games and quizzes, which increases their interest in learning. Through gamification, students are not limited to just learning, but also become more active in the learning process. In chemistry, game elements create opportunities to master skills such as studying chemical reactions, remembering chemical substances, and performing laboratory experiments [4].

Project-based learning provides students with the opportunity to solve real-life problems. In chemistry, project-based learning allows students to conduct independent research and develop creative thinking. For example, practical projects, such as research on renewable energy sources or the chemical production of natural dyes , expand and help students consolidate their

knowledge. Project-based learning allows students to develop not only knowledge, but also the skills to apply it in practice [5].

At the same time, the effectiveness of each method depends on the level of knowledge of students, the organization of the educational process, and the methodological competence of the teacher. It is important to take into account the individual needs of students when using modern pedagogical technologies. Therefore, each approach in the educational process must be carefully selected and adapted to students[6].

CONCLUSION

The use of modern pedagogical approaches in teaching chemistry deepens students' knowledge, develops their independent thinking skills, and forms practical skills. Approaches such as STEAM, problem-based learning, digital technologies, gamification , and project-based learning increase students' active participation in the educational process, ensure interdisciplinary integration, and encourage scientific research. All this increases students' interest in education and further strengthens their knowledge.

, it is important to select each method in accordance with the individual needs and level of knowledge of students. Therefore, to increase the effectiveness of the educational process, teachers need to master modern methodologies and adapt them to students. In particular, the integration of innovative approaches into the education system will develop the process of students' knowledge acquisition not only theoretically, but also practically, which will greatly contribute to the development of science in the future.

In addition, chemistry teachers can begin to use new technologies in the educational process, further increasing student interest and creating opportunities for them to organize the learning process more effectively. Integrated approaches with other disciplines also bring the practical side of chemistry closer to students, providing them with the opportunity to learn how science and technology work in education.

The widespread use of modern pedagogical technologies will play an important role in improving the quality of education in the future and will provide students with deeper and broader skills in studying chemistry. In combination with other approaches, these methods will help make the learning process more effective and interesting for students

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